

Investigation of the Rheological Properties of Fly Ash and Blast Furnace Slag Based Geopolymers

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ABSTRACT

The studies about geopolymers have increased in recent years since these structures can be a sustainable alternative providing less energy consumption and carbon emissions compared to cement in terms of production and application. In this study, the rheological properties of geopolymers were investigated compared to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) for different applications such as the building industry. Firstly, geopolymers were prepared with different ratios of one type of fly ash (FA) to two different types of blast furnace slags (BFS) having different crystallinities, a fixed concentration of NaOH solution, a fixed weight ratio of Na₂SiO₃ to NaOH, and different ratios of the solid to the liquid component. The reactions were monitored by FTIR and XRD to understand the reaction yield, and the results were tried to be correlated with the rheological properties. According to FTIR and XRD results, geopolymers J1, J2, and J3 having a ratio of FA to BFS 50:50, 50:50, and 25:75 respectively had the highest levels of yield as J1 < J2 < J3. According to the controlled shear rate tests, OPC and J3 showed a shear thinning behavior, while J1 and J2 showed a shear thickening behavior. The viscosities of the samples were J1 < J2 < J3 < OPC because the geopolymerization yield of J1 was the smallest one. Since the crystalline structures have less reactivity in terms of geopolymerization, the BFS with higher crystallinity used in J1 led to a lower yield and viscosity. J2 had an excessive alkali liquid because the same solid/liquid ratio of J1 was used in J2, and since the BFS which is more amorphous and reactive was used in J2, this BFS needed less solution for geopolymerization. That solid/liquid ratio led to a higher but inhomogeneous geopolymerization with a slightly higher viscosity of J2 than that of J1. The viscosity of J3 was less than OPC to ~155/s of shear rate. For J3, the viscosity is dominated by a viscous contribution instead of a colloidal one due to the interaction between grains, unlike OPC. Because a gel structure forms at the very early stage of geopolymerization the viscosity of the J3 became lower than that of OPC. According to the amplitude sweep test results, the structural stabilities of geopolymers were lower than that of the OPC, and the loss modulus values of the samples are J1 < J2 < J3 < OPC. According to the frequency test results, the storage modulus values of the samples are J2 < J1 < J3 < OPC, and that means from J2 to OPC, the flow behavior of the samples changed from viscous/liquid-like to elastic/solid-like. However, because of the uncertain data arising from the FS measurement of J1 and J2, only the results of J3 were taken into account in terms of FS test. According to the viscosity recovery test, J3 recovered its viscosity after a certain time more than that of OPC. This result might be obtained because of the domination of the viscous contribution in J3. Because of their very low viscosity values, J1 and J2 could not be measured for the viscosity recovery test.

Keywords: Geopolymer, Ordinary Portland Cement, Rheology, Waste Utilization